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SOCIETY OF KNOWLEDGES AS SPACE OF DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECT OF PERSONALITY

Purpose. In the article the author analyzes the history of the formation of the concept of "knowledge society", stressed the ambiguity of the category "knowledge". We consider the views of various researchers on topics studied question, their difference and contradiction, analyzed the degree of research scholars of the subject. The author of the article pays attention to the integrity and consistency - logical properties of the educational process. The concept of "resources", "intellectual resources". Proven strategic resources of building a "knowledge society" are creativity and intellectual development. **Methodology.** The author in the publication examines the concept of intelligence, its nature from the perspective of the intellect of the person. Reviewed and defined the essence of the new paradigm of education - "Education throughout life", and the element of the new educational paradigm is the concept of fundamentalization of education. **The scientific novelty.** The analysis of the conceptual apparatus, the formation of a new educational paradigm. **Conclusions.** After consideration of all factors and reasons, the author concludes that the scope for the functioning and deployment of intelligence of the individual is the knowledge society.

Key words: society of knowledge, knowledge, intellect, education during all life.

Introduction

The modern information revolution initiated the formation of the phenomenon of the knowledge society, the leading features of which are: 1) the fact that knowledge is a key component in any sphere of human activity and 2) the fact that knowledge is the main product of human activity, its main raw material. Philosophical and pedagogical understanding of the nature and essence of the "knowledge society", particularly in its definition as a medium of personal development, is in the initial state in our literature.

We need to stop the formation of the concept of "knowledge society" and its basic characteristics. In practice the increasing role of knowledge in all spheres of life is the most important regularity of the modern stage of society development. A characteristic feature of modern human activity is the presence of an intellectual component in each product and service. Today the scientific community has not yet formed a unified holistic view of the changes that are happening now in the society, economy, education and industry. However, now there is an active search of new models of social development.

"Knowledge society" becomes one of the key notions of scientific discourse in the beginning of this century. As a stage in social development, following the post-industrial and information society,

the ethos of the "knowledge society" appears to be an extremely urgent problem for the world scientific and educational community. This situation is caused by the fact that the developed countries due to economic development increasingly focused on the service sector, which becomes the basis for drafting the budget. This creates the preconditions for the emergence of a new form of public organization "information society". The problem arises from identifying the specific development of education, science and knowledge in the context of the information society. The problem of the "knowledge society" in the context of global and domestic educational space found fundamental lighting in the works of V. Flint (problem of informatization of society), V. Andrushchenko (organized society and processes of globalization), V. Beha (society of knowledge and entertainments), B. Budzan ("society of knowledge" determines the type of economy), S. Vovcanitcha (increase of knowledge as strategic factor of construction of innovative societies), L. Guberski ("Society of knowledge" is an attribute of development of society (informative society), P. Davydova (Ukrainian society as antipode of society of knowledge ("headless society"), N. Zgurovsky (motion of universities to society of knowledge), V. Kovalerov (problem of education in the context of informative society), I. Kaleniuk (conformities to law of becoming of informative society and economy

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knowledge), V. Lanovoy (prospect development Ukrainian society) and other authors. Informational dimension of the educational space in the era of civilizational transformations are the works A. Sukhomlinsky, A. Verbitsky, V. Larionova, S. Sysoeva and others.

But conceptual analysis of new problems, updated the "knowledge society", shows the divergence of philosophers, educators, sociologists, political scientists, economists on objective substantial characteristics of a given society, which is still being formed. **The aim of the study** is to determine the prerequisites that define the knowledge society as a space deployment of intelligence of the individual. It is in this perspective that the pursuit of science by anyone else of the scientists was not conducted. An important challenge remains the clarification of the definition of a knowledge society that gives the opportunity of personality in the development and realization of their intellectual potential.

However, studies over the last two decades have proven that the field of education (understood in a broad sense as an element of culture) is its base. This database has its specific structure, social functions, and other organizational characteristics. However, internal problems of education remain unexplored: subject-disciplinary, organizational, methodological, legal, management and the like. These findings point to the need for proper philosophical analysis of these questions.

Materials and Methods

Today it becomes clear that education itself is not a private matter but a social technology for the production of the person, his (her) key abilities. Obtaining and using new knowledge becomes a key feature of the new (information) economy. Today knowledge and general education serve not only as a commodity, but also as a factor of social development, as individuals and society as a whole. It should be noted that even in the late twentieth century many Western researchers focus on the role and the powerful importance not only of information but also, to a greater extent on knowledge. This led, naturally, to a new definition of the state of modern society that has the name "society of knowledge".

Regarding the understanding of knowledge as a commodity and education as one of the key elements of the system services, we note that the key point in the adoption of these approaches arose, the

inclusion of education in the context of GATS (General Agreement of Trade in Services – General agreement on trade in services). On this issue researcher J. Tilak is disturbing to notice that the GATS does not differentiate between trade in educational services, selling cars, computers, clothes or financial services, it is logical to make use of privatization and commercialization in higher education, as well as to create the most favorable conditions for international education without barriers for foreign firms regarding access to educational markets [17, p.124].

However, today there is a fairly well-reasoned theory that would substantiate comprehensive historical aspects of the new phenomenon, the essence of which is the desire of most countries to develop an innovative path that will lead to the knowledge society [3, p.161]. The concept of "knowledge society" has a relatively short history, the beginning of which belongs to the second half of the twentieth century - the beginning of XXI century, for the first time the term "knowledge society" was introduced into scientific circulation in 1966, the American researcher R. Lane, who examined the impact of scientific knowledge to the field of public policy and management [11, p.5]. The basis for the concept of the "knowledge society" was made up from the study of Americans F. Mahlup and P. Drucker.

Studying the impact of the role of knowledge on the structure of employment and highlighting the main trends of further development of the knowledge economy F. Mahlup assumed that there are certain quantitative characteristics in the field of education to justify the transition to a new phase of social development, which is qualitatively different from the previous one [11, p.5].

According to the theory of the knowledge economy based on F. Mahlup education is the main resource of the economy because it allows generating high-quality human capital that will determine the prospects of development of production, technology, science. So taking into account this concept economic progress will be determined primarily by the performance of intellectual capital, not of physical resources. But in this case the knowledge society is explored through the prism of the economic paradigm.

Another author P. Drucker pays attention to deep social changes, but not only the analysis of the dynamics of technology development and economic growth. The researcher believes that the basis of all three stages of increasing role of

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knowledge (the industrial revolution, a revolution in productivity and the revolution in management) is a fundamental change in the value of knowledge. According to P. Drucker, we have gone from knowledge (in the singular) to knowledge (in the plural), i.e. to numerous fields of knowledge. In earlier times, knowledge was of a General nature. According to P. Drucker, scientific discipline assigns "craft" in the category of methodology, for example, production technology, scientific methodology, quantitative method or differential diagnosis (medicine), when each such methodology converts private expertise into the system, individual cases and events – in information [9].

Consequently, there is reason to believe that American researcher P. Drucker "knowledge society" is following the information society, the stage of social development, in which a special place belongs to education and management; intelligent society, where knowledge in a number of resources such as capital, land or labor has a dominant place.

It must be emphasized that P. Drucker conceptualized and supplemented disparate currents in Economics, sociology, social psychology within the framework of a unified system with largely socio-philosophical ideas about the "knowledge society". In the "knowledge society" P. Drucker emphasizes the role of education, considers its main task to be is to teach the individual to learn, making the knowledge society become a medium for the qualitative development of intellectual potential of the members of this society.

In the future, the concept of "knowledge society" was developed in the works of D. Bell, N. Stehr, R. Reich, P. Weingart and other authors.

Professor at a Canadian University N. Stehr, who has made a significant contribution to the establishment of the concept of "knowledge society" as an independent scientific and philosophical concept, indicates the activity aspect of the knowledge. The researcher addresses the issues of knowledge transfer in the context of globalization, noting, along with the empowerment of the society, its fragility and vulnerability [11, p.6].

Speaking about the fragility of modern society in the framework of postmodern philosophical tradition S. Bauman notes that today the most valuable quality is the flexibility: all components must be flexible and mobile, so they can be instantly regroup, without having too strong links between components: strength and persistence brought the curse of the day not allowing to adapt to quickly

changing and unpredictable world [1, p.290-291].

And one of the influential representatives of sociology mobile notes J. Urry leads as an example this sandy metaphor: "Consider a heap of sand; if an extra grain of sand is placed on top it may stay there or it may cause a small avalanche. The system is self-organized, however, the effects of local changes can vary enormously... the heap will maintain itself to the critical height and we cannot know in advance what will happen to any individual action or what its consequence will be for the pile of sand" [18, p.198].

E. Toffler argues that the field of knowledge is the axis around which new technologies, economic growth, social stratification are organized, for every dollar that is invested in the economy of the Third wave, you have few dollars to invest in human capital - in education; the most important thing is the transformation not machines, and people upgrading their consciousness, the transition to understanding the primary importance of culture in the life of human communities [12, p.47].

You can make an intermediate conclusion that the main goal of a modern, developed society is the construction of a "knowledge society". In relation to this definition, most scientists are exploring the "knowledge society" in the light of the information revolution, which shows the transformation of knowledge into a key component of any sphere of the subject area.

In our view, the main result of the analysis of the concept of "knowledge society" is that every conscious person of this society needs to learn all his life. In this context, social development has been published for educational paradigm. For "the knowledge society" it is necessary to shape the environment for comprehensive development of personality, a special role should be given to the development of intellectual potential of the individual.

However, we are aware of the fact that the knowledge society is not formed by itself from information. It is clear that increased information does not necessarily lead to the growth of knowledge.

In this way with us is E. Naumkin, who argues that it is necessary that the means of obtaining, processing, interpreting and using this information should also be adequate to the task of producing and using knowledge for the development of human society, both in spiritual and material spheres, the notion of "information society" is determined

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by the advances of technology, while the concept of "knowledge society" refers to the broader social, psychological, ethical, axiological and other parameters [8, p.34].

As we can see "knowledge" is a key component of the knowledge society and the basis of intelligence personality, because in such a society the overwhelming majority of the active population performs as a primary professional activity - mental activity. In addition, the acquisition of knowledge in this society is not limited by the walls of educational institutions (in space), or completion of primary education (in time), and life becomes constant and imperative in the new world which is becoming more complex, where everyone in the course of a lifetime may be required to perform various tasks, it becomes necessary to study all life.

It is necessary to emphasize the ambiguity of the category of "knowledge". This category is revealed with sometimes radically different psychological, philosophical and pedagogical science. So, the researcher N. Korableva notes that knowledge should be understood as everything that is interpreted as knowledge in real human life, that is all that is cognitive in nature, as the study of knowledge does not start with a fixing concept, but with the building of the socio-historical picture of the cognitive situation and the subsequent superimposing it onto the knowledge that is to be analyzed [5, p.37].

A. Singaevskaya rightly argues that philosophy usually examines the phenomenon of knowledge as a fundamental mental category, which characterizes the awareness of specific individual objective reality and reflects a person's worldview, however, knowledge also functions as an impersonal phenomenon, as a public good, collective intelligence and becomes the dominant resource, the main driving force and organizing principle of society development and also the "knowledge society" [10, p.70].

It is clear that education as an institution is directly related to the formation of knowledge of the personality, although the sources of knowledge exist outside the educational and institutional space. From the standpoint of pedagogy, knowledge is understood as a form of existence, as well as specific tools for systematization of the results of the cognitive activity of the individual. [9, p.141].

Regarding the role of non-linear thinking in ed-

ucational processes, O. Uvarkina states the following: "Referring to the experience of the Western information society with its established forms of education, it should be noted that the modern education system also has moved away from classic (Cartesians) linear circuits, rejecting the idea of universalism and encyclopaedism education at all levels" [13, c.212].

According to the approach proposed by N. Sterom, knowledge is a universal property of man, and his dual nature is characterized, first, by the acquisition of practical experience and, secondly, by the basis for scaling up (i.e. next) knowledge, this is the main change in the model for the development of education in the intellectual development of the knowledge society [15].

Knowledge, according to the researcher, can be defined as "the ability to act" as the ability "to set in motion", and the specifics of the current stage is that the number of occupations associated with knowledge-based work is growing, while the share of jobs requiring limited cognitive skills is rapidly declining, and as a result fewer people are employed in the sphere of material production [15].

So, indeed, knowledge has become a key component of the knowledge society and also the fundamental basis of the intellect of the person. As for the knowledge society as a modern form of social development it is rapidly evolving, stimulating perpetual mass increase and diffusion of knowledge.

The etymology of the term "knowledge" shows that it is formed from the verb "know". Modern scholars argue that knowledge is not divided into parts in the human consciousness, they are integral and inseparable in word formation. Undoubtedly, obtaining knowledge is important, the role of information and communication (transportation) of this static resource is not moved by the vectors of space and time, because the basis of communication is information.

Knowledge by its nature is an information product. Information after consumption does not disappear as for example conventional financial product. In order to be ready and accurate knowledge of a particular person information undergoes comprehension, critical evaluation, conscious mental processing, its own mental interpretation, thus consciously fixing the condition of the objective world. But the instance of the consciousness with ignorance of something does not represent his (her) knowledge instantly and automatical-

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ly.

But in our opinion, educational approach focusing on the role of education in intelligence development pushes the problem of cultural transformation factors of intellectual development, the problems of formation of the environment for personality development to the fore. Intelligence is understood as the principal means of acquiring knowledge, and in the "knowledge society" knowledge is the main product of human activity.

Due to intellectual ability, modern postmodern man is able to comprehend its purpose (professional orientation), to form professional competence, to assess his (her) own choice during school years. Therefore, the formation of knowledge (transfer students, acquisition of knowledge) is a key component of the educational process in the "knowledge society".

The changes taking place in modern society on the path of becoming a "knowledge society" in a new way highlighted the problem of the organization of educational space, because it needs to adequately meet the modern imperatives, in particular, to prepare and educate the necessary personnel to support the operation of production and economy and their development. The modern paradigm of education is losing its relevance in the "knowledge society", therefore, there is a need for new principles, methods and technologies of education and training.

One of the key requirements of the system of education and upbringing in the conditions of formation of the "society of knowledge" is learning skills to learn.

In the modern "knowledge society" knowledge creation is a key component of the educational process. Therefore, the knowledge gained in the process of their formation gives members of the public the opportunity to respond to the following questions, according to S. Yablochkova:

"What?" (analytical knowledge, which is used for the analysis of the causes of certain phenomena, events, and interpretation of tangible and intangible properties of objects);

"How?" (pragmatic or factual knowledge, which are required for appropriate solutions, including managerial);

"Why?" (target knowledge that helps you identify the goal, to predict the results of the implementation of a specific process or set of actions);

"How exactly?" (technological knowledge, which help to understand and design the sequence,

algorithm or technology to perform a set of actions and their structure);

"Under what conditions?" (situational knowledge, which characterize the conditions of implementation and development of certain processes, phenomena, events and functioning objects) [16].

And before the philosophy of education there are a number of new problems. And the first of them consists in a fundamental review of the existing teaching paradigm.

Researcher T. Upland writes that you can highlight features that distinguish competence from traditional notions of knowledge, abilities, skills, experience; its integrated nature; the correlation with the value-semantic characteristics of the individual; the practice-oriented focus [2].

So, really, competence-based approach not only reduces the role of knowledge in the system of the educational process, and optimizes and organizes it.

Cognition, scientific knowledge, and also an open system which operates on the principle of development are important in educational reform in the transition to a "knowledge society". And it is quite natural and logical the nature of this process will differ from the process in the early twentieth century, and even a few decades ago. As it is rightly pointed out by G. Myhaylishyn, "the main feature and the basis of the new world order of the third Millennium is the transformation of scientific knowledge in key strategic and commercial product, conditions of access and use of which is determined by the leadership and the relations between countries in a new global community. The division of countries into producers and consumers of knowledge is becoming a major geopolitical factor in the world. Confront here is not ideal and material, knowledge and the subject is assumed in the concept of materialization of knowledge, and knowledge in the form of a commercial product - product-for-sale - knowledge in the form of cognitive (creative) product" [7, p.457].

Thus, the integrity and consistency are logical properties of the educational process. They objectively exist precisely so far as the modern "knowledge society" demonstrates the need for the formation of both the environment harmonious development of the intellect of the person. Hence objectively derive the requirements for unity of education, upbringing, the need to develop pupil/student as a person, focus on the comprehensive

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development of intelligence, personality and the like.

Strategic resources of building a "knowledge society" brought creativity and intellectual development. In these conditions, an integral part of preserving the social status of an active member of the society becomes continuous education, which is aimed at building skills of each day to find new knowledge, to adequately perceive and productively apply. But this new knowledge and new information need to be comprehensive.

In contemporary postmodern society of knowledge new characteristics, namely the synergistic nature, are acquired. The world is presented as a complex and dynamic system that is constantly evolving. Here man is not sovereign, but only a part of nature. The impact of a changing world on any system (and humans) requires appropriate responses and changes. But it could dissolve in the chaos of constant change and to preserve the viability, if not the stability of structures. Therefore, this combination of variability and stability already has synergistic nature because this synergy works in the fields of dynamic balance between stability and variability. The property of the inherent dynamic stability is of complex nonlinear systems, that explore the synergy.

The spirit of reductionism dominates in the content of modern educational process. The content of education should consider a much wider, namely as pedagogically adapted to broadcast social experience of all mankind. The society that is on the verge of an ecological crisis, in order to survive it is time to move to a qualitatively new level of socio-cultural development, and its basis is formed by patterns of activity and behaviour based on the knowledge of the mechanisms of self-organization of both nature and humanity.

In these circumstances as the aim of education and education it self changed: the person does not identify with a particular profession chosen for life. She (he) throughout her (his) life changes a profession several times, working on various projects that require constant training and retraining.

The scientific novelty

Humanity's entrance into the information society naturally puts forward innovative education requirements. These requirements resulted in the need to change the configuration (models) for the development of education. If the essence of the old paradigm can be expressed as "Education for life",

the essence of the new paradigm of education can be expressed as "Education throughout life".

The task of the educational process in the "knowledge society" raises welfare society fundamentally prepared by competent professionals, able to creatively apply the latest results of modern science and technology, to use innovative technologies, responding flexibly to the requests of a market economy. Therefore, the most important element of the new educational paradigm is the concept of fundamentalization of education, which understands the fundamental nature as a category for estimating the overall quality of education and the education of a person.

Indeed, modern universities in creating curricula and in its research activities should focus on fundamentality of knowledge that they produce as a result of scientific research, and broadcast in the learning process: it is about fundamentality as the openness and clarity for investors from other countries, and the universities themselves must be aware of the national-supranational duality as one of its fundamental characteristics [9, p.79].

Conclusions

Therefore, the formation of a "knowledge society" requires the solution of an important historic task that is to understand the ways of ensuring the full realization of the creative potential of each individual man, that, undoubtedly, is the condition not only of the development and its qualitative functioning, but also the actual physical and spiritual survival. Therefore, new educational path (in most cases it is the individual) is able to solve these problems, focusing on the requests, needs, opportunities, potential of each individual person.

Modern education is in a state of change paradigms. The last paradigm is guided by industry-specific training and pre-known market specialties and qualifications. The task of education in this case is to provide the customer with basic knowledge in one or more directions in education - natural, human or technical. Educational production should capture changes in demand and quickly embody it in your programs.

At the present stage of social development the acquired knowledge is an important indicator of the level of employment and investment in education and science - the condition of full employment in the future.

Discussion and Conclusions

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Thus we investigated the knowledge society as a productive space deployment of the intellect of the person. It is shown that the modern national education system is an independent socio-economic sector and represents a set of educational programs, educational institutions, governments

and state-public associations. It is in constant motion and takes into account in its development not only of national experience, but also global trends and traditions, leading among which is the formation of a "knowledge society".

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СУСПІЛЬСТВО ЗНАНЬ ЯК ПРОСТІР РОЗГОРТАННЯ ІНТЕЛЕКТУ ОСОБИСТОСТІ

Мета. У статті автором проаналізовано історію формування поняття «суспільство знань», підкреслена неоднозначність категорії «знання». Розглянуті погляди різних дослідників на тематику, що вивчається, їх відмінність та протиріччя, проаналізовано ступінь дослідженості предмета вченими. Автор статті звертає увагу на комплексність і системність - закономірні властивості освітнього процесу. Розглянуто поняття «ресурсів», «інтелектуальних ресурсів». Доведено, що стратегічними ресурсами побудови «суспільства знань» є творчий потенціал, а також інтелектуальний розвиток людини. **Методологія** дослідження полягає в застосуванні компаративного аналізу. Автор публікації розглядає поняття інтелекту, його сутність у ракурсі інтелекту особистості людини. Розглянуто і визначено сутність нової парадигми освіти - «Освіта впродовж усього життя», а елементом нової освітньої парадигми постає концепція фундаменталізації освіти. **Новизна.** Проведено аналіз понятійного апарату, розглянуто систему формування нової освітньої парадигми. **Висновки.** Після розгляду усіх факторів і причин автор публікації робить висновок про те, що простором для функціонування і розвитку інтелекту особистості є суспільство знань.

Ключові слова: суспільство знань, знання, інтелект, освіта протягом усього життя.

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ОБЩЕСТВО ЗНАНИЙ КАК ПРОСТОР РАСКРЫТИЯ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ЛИЧНОСТИ

Цель. В статье автором проанализирована история формирования понятия «общество знаний», подчеркнута неоднозначность категории «знание». Рассмотрены взгляды различных исследователей на тематику изучаемого вопроса, их различие и противоречие, проанализирована степень исследованности предмета учеными. Автор в статье обращает внимание на комплексность и системность - закономерные свойства образовательного процесса. Рассмотрено понятие «ресурсов», «интеллектуальных ресурсов». Доказано, что стратегическими ресурсами построения «общества знаний» являются творческий потенциал, а также интеллектуальное развитие человека. **Методология** исследования строится на использовании компаративного анализа. Автор в публикации рассматривает понятие интеллекта, его сущность в ракурсе интеллекта личности человека. Рассмотрена и определена сущность новой парадигмы образования - «Образование на протяжении всей жизни», а элементом новой образовательной парадигмы предстает концепция фундаментализации образования. **Новизна.** Проведен анализ понятийного аппарата, рассмотрено систему формирования новой образовательной парадигмы. **Выводы.** После рассмотрения всех факторов и причин автор публикации делает вывод о том, что простором для функционирования и разворачивания интеллекта личности является общество знаний.

Ключевые слова: общество знаний, знание, интеллект, образование на протяжении всей жизни.

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